

PROVIDING TRANSPORT USERS WITH HIGH-QUALITY TRANSPORTATION SERVICES

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Abstract: This article presents the basic concepts of providing transport users with the quality of transport services. The article covers the main terms of railway transport in passenger transportation. There are also comments on the main aspects of passenger services.

Keywords: Railway station, railway station complex, station activity, stopping point, passenger train, luggage storage room, carrier, passenger.

Introduction.

Railway station - a subdivision of public railway transport that carries out technological operations with trains and other vehicles (receiving and dispatching, shunting operations, etc.), as well as operations for receiving and issuing baggage, cargo baggage and passenger service;

Railway station complex - a combination of railway station and its surrounding territory, structures, buildings and structures connected to a physical, technological or other railway station and subject to a single legal regime for operation and development;

Station activity - the activity of servicing users and consumers of a railway station, consisting of the management of a railway station, including their design, construction, repair, and operation. Stopping point - a stopping point intended exclusively for the boarding and disembarking of passengers;

passenger train - a train designed for the carriage of passengers on all types of railway communication. may contain baggage, mail and (or) mail-baggage cars;

luggage storage room - a specially equipped room for short-term storage of hand luggage;

carrier - a legal entity that has a license for the right to carry out activities for the carriage of passengers and has undertaken under a contract the obligation to deliver a passenger, baggage, cargo baggage entrusted to it by the sender from the point of departure to the designated address by public railway transport, as well as to transfer baggage, cargo baggage to an authorized person (recipient) for its acceptance;

Transportation documents - documents for processing the carriage of passengers, baggage, cargo, baggage, and rolling stock (waybills, waybills, shipping documents, waybills, ticket, baggage receipt, cargo, baggage receipt);

passenger - a citizen (individual) who has travel documents and travels by train;

hand luggage - easily transportable items and items, regardless of the type and appearance of packaging, which, by their dimensions and weight (not exceeding 180 cm in three dimensions and usually not exceeding 36 kg in weight), easily fit in the places provided for their placement in passenger cars;

baggage - items, goods, and other material assets carried by a passenger and located in and with the passenger car during the trip;

freight baggage - the object of railway transportation carried by passenger and mail-baggage trains;

Railway station services consist of activities aimed at meeting the needs of users and consumers.

Figure 1. Providing transport users with high-quality transportation services

Tasks and principles of transport service in passenger transportation.

The formation and production of services in the transport market requires systematic and regular study of the population's needs, desires, and demand for passenger transportation.

Demand is the desire of passengers based on purchasing power. People's desires are practically limitless in themselves, but their resources are limited. People can only satisfy the needs that they can afford to spend on purchasing more goods and services than others.

Main part.

Passenger transportation is considered not as an activity that adds to the consumer value of the main service - transport, but as a safety system that allows improving the conditions of passenger movement on railway transport, increasing its competitiveness in the transport market.

The obligation to offer and perform a complex of transport services to the population. Passengers must be informed about the services provided at the initial

and final stations (stations) and on the route. Passenger companies, SMs and their service structures must assume obligations under contracts that can only guarantee, and the order accepted for the performance of services must be a binding document for all involved organizations and structures.[1].

The technical level of the passenger rolling stock and its equipment (removable and non-removable inventory and equipment) must be sufficient for the service technology; otherwise, the corresponding service quality cannot be achieved. The consumer is interested not in the manufacturer's problems, but in their own; the quality of service should not suffer from technical shortcomings on trains and at railway stations. This leads to the need to create special original technical solutions for service technology [2-4].

Effect of information about services. The passenger company needs to listen to and respond accordingly to customer reviews and assessments, information about competitors' service behavior and techniques that can be provided by the service complex, train crews, passenger transportation segments, departments related to the sale of goods and services.

Voluntary use of services by the client. SM employees, the passenger transportation company, and their structures should not assign the service to the customer.

Service (flexible) flexibility. Services should be offered to passengers as single or as few as necessary, the combination of which is determined by the customer [5].

Convenience of service. The service must be provided in one place, at the same time, and in a form suitable for the client (passenger).

The main characteristics of service quality are:

- Standardization and expansion of the range of services in high-comfort waiting rooms;
- provision of banking and wireless internet access services;

- provision of express delivery services for small mail items by passenger trains;

- provision of services for booking and selling tickets for other types of passenger transport; organization of accommodation in hotels at railway stations and rooms for long-term recreation;

- provision of services for the sale and booking of tickets for excursions and other cultural events; organization of meetings in front of train cars; expansion of the range of household and office services provided at railway stations (cleaning clothes and shoes, repair of watches, repair of metal equipment, telephone, Internet and Fax services, etc.);

- installation of automatic storage rooms with the possibility of hourly payment at railway stations; installation of vending machines for hot and cold drinks, soft drinks, hygiene products, as well as payment terminals (mobile communication, payment for utilities, etc.);

-opening of pharmacy kiosks.

Legal Basis of Passenger Transportation Services.

A distinctive feature of transport services is the provision of various types of services: transportation, food, accommodation, excursions, etc. Therefore, there are many legal documents regulating passenger transportation services. The main regulatory legal acts regulating the management of passenger transportation include:

Charter (Regulation) of Railway Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

It defines the rights, duties, and obligations of railways and regulates the basic conditions for the carriage of passengers using railway transport, as well as passengers, baggage, cargo baggage, and mail [6-7].

Passenger transportation and travel regulations. Includes transportation conditions, passengers, payment system (price list 10-02), set of standards, and standards for passenger service. They also specifically include passenger

transportation conditions related to the free passage of various categories of passengers on railways, tourist transportation conditions, migrants, and others. Collections of transportation rules and tariffs are periodically published. They introduce additions and amendments to the rules of transport and passenger transportation.

Agreement on International Passenger Transportation. The member states of the Commonwealth, the Republic of Latvia, the Republic of Lithuania, and the Republic of Estonia establish a direct international procedure for the carriage of passengers, baggage, and cargo on the roads; the rules of military transportation determine the issuance of military transportation documents for passengers, baggage, and cargo, the conditions for their execution, and others.

Basic regulatory documents in the field of services provided, various laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan (for example, the Law “On Railway Transport of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, “On Technical Regulation” etc.), state standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international standards (ISO), interstate standards (GOST), rules for the carriage of passengers, baggage and cargo baggage by rail of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The relationship between the need for transport services and prices.

Demand for passenger transportation and the amount of prices are closely interconnected.

Marketing in the field of passenger transportation is the activity of the passenger complex, aimed at studying and best satisfying the demand for services related to the transportation of baggage and cargo, with the goal of obtaining a certain profit by transport service enterprises. In the field of passenger transportation, marketing is the activity of a passenger complex aimed at studying and best satisfying the demand for services related to the transportation of baggage and cargo, the goal of which is to obtain a certain profit from transport service enterprises.

Passenger transportation marketing includes:

analysis of the state and dynamics of consumer demand in the market

transport services;

identification and study of consumer benefits;

Different assessment of the external environment and the level of competition in the transport market;

determination of the potential of the transport services market for the population and the market share of railway transport;

market segmentation; identification of existing and prospective segments of the transport services market for the population;

pricing policy;

development of advertising activities and stimulation of demand for passenger transportation;

provision and development of new transport services to the population.

The result of passenger transportation marketing is the adoption of effective management decisions to ensure the involvement of maximum passenger traffic in railway transport due to a competitive tariff policy and the provision of transport services to the population at the required level of volume and quality.

So, finding ways to attract and increase passengers

railway transport should conduct comprehensive research on the transport market, i.e., the efficiency of passenger transportation.

For financially secure passengers - safety, fatigue on the road, convenience, adherence to the schedule, travel speed, ease of ticket purchase, staff attitude, ticket price, departure and arrival time, types of services.

- for low-income passengers - this is the price of the ticket, safety, travel speed, travel and comfort, fatigue level, etc.

Passenger transportation segmentation.

The study of consumers of transport services requires a thorough analysis and forecasting of market conditions and an assessment of the impact on the financial results of the carrier.

It is necessary to identify ways to attract additional cargo, including new shippers or other modes of transport, commercial structures, private individuals, as well as to solve the issues of expanding transport services.

The main method of studying consumers of transport services is market segmentation, that is, firstly, it is determined for which groups of cargo owners a specific type of transport service is intended, as well as in which industries and modes of transportation transportation is carried out, and secondly, what technical and technological indicators (parameters) are important for improving the quality and profitability of transportation, and what other indicators need to be worked on to fully satisfy customer demand. Only then can market capacity, real calculation, the volume of investments in the development of the industry, and new technologies in the transportation process be determined.

Conclusion. To attract passengers to railway transport, it is important, first of all, to improve the quality of passenger transportation, especially the implementation of a number of measures aimed at improving safety, reducing the speed of trains and transportation costs for the population.

Among the factors used by cargo owners, price (tariff) is one of the most important, and this should be taken into account when studying the need for services and determining the relationship between demand and price.

Each of these parameters can be a principle of market segmentation. On this basis, railway companies identify and serve broad segments - groups of buyers of transport services, differing in the nature of demand and procurement.

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